

Questionnaire for Experts on Vertical Farming in Residential Balconies

Vertical farming is exactly what it sounds like: farming **on vertical surfaces (stacked layers)** rather than traditional, horizontal agriculture. It often incorporates **controlled-environment agriculture**, which aims to optimize plant growth, and soilless farming techniques. By using vertically stacked layers, much more food can be produced on the same amount of land (or even less).

This survey aims to gather the perspectives of **academics, architects, and designers** on the potential integration of vertical farming in residential building balconies. Your responses will help in understanding the design considerations, aesthetics, and challenges involved. Besides, your responses will help us understand the perceived benefits and challenges associated with this innovative approach of vertical farming. The **questionnaire consists of four parts** in addition to the basic demographic data.

A. Demographic Data:

1. Profession:
2. Years of work experience in the field:

B. General queries:

3. What would be your primary motivation for including vertical farming in your residential design projects?
 - Sustainability and environmental benefits.
 - Economic benefits (e.g., food production).
 - Visual and aesthetic appeal.
 - Client demand or market trend.
 - Resident well-being.
 - Other (please specify).

C. Design Considerations and Challenges:

4. Do you believe that vertical farming can be effectively integrated into existing residential balconies?
 - No.
 - Yes, with minor adjustments and modifications.
 - Yes, with major adjustments and modifications.
5. Do you think incorporating vertical farming on existing balconies would require significant modifications to the existing architectural design layout?
 - No.
 - Yes, with minor modifications.
 - Yes, with major modifications.
6. What challenges would you be most worried about when adopting vertical farms in residential settings?
 - Structural stability.
 - Construction.
 - Feasibility (Cost and budget).
 - Visual clutter.
 - Maintenance.
 - Other (please specify).

7. Within the structural challenges, which one have you encountered or would expect when designing vertical farming systems would be the most critical?
 - Weight of vertical farming systems (soil, water, and crops).
 - Balcony size and layout.
 - Wind and weather resistance.
 - Drainage and irrigation management.
 - Other (please specify).

8. What construction-related barrier is most likely to impact the implementation of vertical farming on balconies?
 - High construction and installation costs.
 - Complex installation processes.
 - Limited availability of suitable materials.
 - Regulatory restrictions.
 - Other (please specify).

9. What maintenance challenges would you expect from vertical farming on residential balconies?
 - Regular irrigation, watering, and drainage.
 - Pest control.
 - Structural wear and tears.
 - System (Soil and vegetation) durability and repair.
 - Resident involvement and knowledge.
 - Humidity.
 - Other (please specify).

10. What is the biggest design challenge in incorporating vertical farming into residential balconies?
 - Balcony area.
 - Balcony proportion (length to width ratio).
 - Balcony shape (Rectangular, circular, irregular, etc.).
 - Balcony façade relation (recessed, extruded, shaded, etc.).
 - Other (please specify).

D. Aesthetic Impact:

11. What is the most challenge do you foresee in maintaining the visual harmony of the building facades while incorporating vertical farming elements?
 - Farming colors.
 - Farming coverage area in proportion to the façade area.
 - Farming elements size and distribution over the facade.
 - Farming type.
 - Other (please specify).

E. Climate and Environment:

12. Which of the following environmental benefits would be the most effective in implementing vertical farming systems for balconies?

- Decrease temperature.
- Improve air quality.
- Rainwater management.
- Provide shading.
- Lower Carbon footprint.
- Urban biodiversity (reduce land use required for traditional farming).
- Other (please specify).

F. Regulations and Building Codes:

13. Do you think current building codes and regulations support the implementation of vertical farming on residential balconies?

- Yes.
- No.
- Need updates.

G. Cost Benefits and Implications:

14. In your view, do the potential costs associated with installing and maintaining vertical farms outweigh their benefits for residents?

- Highly outweigh.
- Slightly outweigh.
- Depends on the residents' treatment for vertical farming (Way of investment, for use, or commercial).
- Don't outweigh.

15. How much influence do you think vertical farming could have on increasing property value in residential buildings due to its sustainability and self-sufficiency aspects?

- Major increase.
- Moderate increase.
- Minor increase.
- No significant impact.

H. Proposed Vertical Farming Alternatives Assessment:

16. From your point of view, which alternative may pose a greater structural concern for the building?

- Option 1.
- Option 2.
- Option 3.

17. From your point of view, based on the prior mentioned challenges in the questionnaire's previous parts, which alternative is likely to require more maintenance?

- Option 1.
- Option 2.
- Option 3.

18. From your point of view, which alternative can better support residents' connection to nature?
- Option 1.
 - Option 2.
 - Option 3.
19. From your point of view, which alternative contributes most effectively to the aesthetic appeal of the residential building?
- Option 1.
 - Option 2.
 - Option 3.
20. In your opinion, which alternative contributes the most to improving the environmental conditions inside the residential unit?
- Option 1.
 - Option 2.
 - Option 3.
21. From your perspective, arrange the design options **from the least to the most** in terms of the required interventions/modifications to the residential building.
- Option 1.
 - Option 2.
 - Option 3.
22. From your expertise, arrange the design options **from the lowest to the highest** in terms of the associated costs for installing the design options.
- Option 1.
 - Option 2.
 - Option 3.

Thank you for taking the time to complete this questionnaire. Your insights are invaluable for understanding the role of vertical farming in understanding the multifaceted benefits/challenges of vertical farming.